

LINGUISTIC TYPOLOGY (APPEARANCE OF WORDS, PARTS OF SPEECH)

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Abstract: This article mainly about old and modern year linguistic typology, and some data related to parts of speech. It also includes classification of word groups in modern English and Uzbek as well as characteristics of words.

Key words and phrases: linguistics, typology, parts of speech, word, lexicon

Scientist who found a description for “word”, semantic and phonological units, parts of speech, linguistic typology, lexical and lexicon – grammatical meanings, morphological forms, role of words in speech, Leonard Bloomfield, said that: “Word is a minimum free form”. Word is known as the smallest naming unit of the languages. It shows that a great number and are made up of smaller units, each possessing sound – form and meaning. The term “word” denotes the basic unit of a given language resulting from the association of particular meaning with a particular group of grammatical employment. Therefore, simultaneously a semantic, grammatical and phonological unit. Every language has its own classes which are called parts of speech. In modern linguistic one of the common problem is parts of speech. The theoretical side of this matter is that subject issue of the theoretical grammar. Thus, we should base our comparison of system of parts of speech on the generally acknowledged opinions of grammarians. In the beginning of developing of linguistic typology tried to respond the matter of what could serve the basis for classifying the languages into “more primitive” and “more developed”. However, very soon it became clear that this starting point was incorrect: it turned to be impossible to make a judgement on the level of development of a language basing

on its typological characteristics. There is a language which perfectly developed. It is going to be Chinese language. Yet it has not letters. Old years of linguistic science development, history of linguistics turn bound with the history of notion and cognition. The classification of word groups in modern English and Uzbek is determined by the following characteristics of words. They are:

- Lexical and grammatical meanings.
- The generality of morphological forms for words belonging to a particular group.
- The role of words in speech.

When we approach the first characteristics or clearly say lexical and grammatical meaning of words, lexical meaning is dominant in content words, whereas grammatical meaning is dominant in function words, but in neither is grammatical meaning absent. Grammatical words include prepositions, articles, conjunctions, and some adverbs. Therefore, the differences between lexical and grammatical structure is often put in term of open as opposed to closed categories being open and the grammatical ones being closed. Next morphological characteristics of a word. Morphology is the study of words and their parts. Morphemes is part of morphology. It is divided into:

- Prefixes
- Suffixes
- Roots.

General morphological process involved in the formation of new words. Five major morphological process that affect roots, and stems and which lead to the production of new words. The last characteristics of words is that the role of words in speech. Words have meaning and when organized in proper grammatical structures, that meaning is transmitted to provide communication. When words no longer hold to their meaning, then communication is hampered and became difficult to understand. Also words are a means for us to express and describe our experiences, emotions, and feelings. Words have power. Their meaning crystallizes

perceptions that shape our beliefs, drive our behaviour, and ultimately, create our world.

References:

1. Dushatova, S. (2022). EVFEMIZM TUSHUNCHASI TAHLILI.
2. Dushatova, S. (2022). LINGUISTIC AND SOCIAL ORIGINATION OF TABOOS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 318-321.
3. Dushatova, S., & Tursunaliyev, M. (2022). CHET TILLARINI O'RGANISHNING INSON RIVOJLANISHIGA TASIRI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 133-138.
4. Dushatova, S., & Azamov, M. (2022, November). SO'Z TURKUMLARI TASNIFI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 89-95).
5. Dushatova, S., & qizi Norinboyeva, D. J. (2022). CHET TILIDA NUTQNI TINGLAB TUSHUNISH VA UNDA FRAZEOLOGIZMLARNING O'RNI. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(7), 66-71.
6. Dushatova, S., & Burgutova, G. (2022). CHET TILLARINI BILISHNING FOYDALARI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(8), 40-45.
7. Dushatova, S., & Mamajonova, S. (2022). "ICEBERG PRINCIPLE" AS A STYLISTIC FEATURE OF E. HEMINGWAY'S SHORT STORY "THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1931-1934.
8. Shokhsanam, D., & Abdukarimova, M. (2022, December). THE ADVANTAGES OF BOOKS IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE DEDICATED TO THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY* (Vol. 1, No. 9, pp. 169-171).
9. Shokhsanam, D., & Makhmudova, M. (2022). BENEFITS OF DAILY READING. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(8), 28-32.

10. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & qizi Qodiraliyeva, N. I. (2022). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4, 1(5)*, 63-67.
11. Zafar, J. (2022). Linguistic and Cultural Problems in Translation. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(12)*, 55-57.
12. Shohsanam, D., & Dildoraxon, R. (2022). Best Ways of Vocabulary Memorisation in Foreign Language Learning. *Academia Open, 7*, 10-21070.
13. Ashurbaeva, R. K. (2021). Ways of effective Implementation of Integration. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 10*.
14. Xaitov, L. A. (2021, December). THE ISSUE OF SUSTENANCE AND PROFESSION IN HAKIM TERMIZI'S WORK "BAYANUL KASB" ("DESCRIPTION OF THE PROFESSION"). In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 67-69).
15. Хаитов, Л. А. (2014). Значение эстетического воспитания в развитии личности студента педагогического вуза. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал, (10)*, 40-44.
16. Azamatovich, X. L. (2021). The Concept of Heart In The Treatises Of Hakim Termizi. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE, 2(3)*, 63-67.
17. Azamatovich, K. L. (2020). The role of the Hakim Termizi architectural complex in visiting tourism in Uzbekistan. *Вопросы науки и образования, (9 (93))*, 27-31.
18. Yuldasheva, D. THE IMPORTANCE OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING AND GROUP WORK IN ENGLISH CLASSES. *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych.*, 100.
19. Yuldasheva, D. (2022). METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TOURISM DIRECTIONS). *Science and innovation, 1(B7)*, 1498-1501.

20. Ашурбаева, Р. К. (2020). Интеграционный подход в системе образования. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 12 (64), pp. 61-63). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості.
21. Yuldasheva, D., & Ashurbayeva, R. Asadova Sh., Yusupova D. Use of an Integrative Research on the Education System. Scopus: *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)* ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8 Issue-4, November 2019.